

Traditional medicinal knowledge by Valmiki tribe of Paderu agency, Alluri Seetharama Raju District, Andhra Pradesh, India

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Abstract:

The *Valmiki's* are one of the Adivasi tribal communities of Paderu region of Alluri Seetharama Raju district. Extensive field studies were undertaken in order to study the utilization of wild medicinal plants which has resulted in the collection of 31 species belonging to 31 families. Three plant species and 22 practices were found to be new or less known.

Keywords: Ethnomedicine, Traditional medicine, Valmiki, tribe, Alluri Seetharama Raju district, Andhra Pradesh

I. Introduction

Traditional medicinal knowledge represents a rich and diverse practices, beliefs, and understandings related to health and healing, developed over generations by indigenous and local communities. The Valmiki tribe is one of the Adivasi tribes residing in the Paderu agency of Alluri Sitharama Raju District in Andhra Pradesh. They claim to be the descendants of great saint VALMIKI, the author of Ramayana and the name itself is derived from the Sanskrit word VALMIKAMU meaning termite hill. Most of the Valmiki tribe speak Adivasi Telugu, except those in areas close to Orissa state who speak Oriya. Few people speak their own tribal dialect (Kupia) to which there is no script. Marriages by mutual consent, elopement, widow marriages and divorce are permissible. These are agriculturists and forest labourers. They practice Podu cultivation on the slopes of hill. The family is considered as the basic unit and also gives importance to large kinship units like lineage.

Alluri Sitharama Raju District is one of the North Eastern districts of Andhra Pradesh. The Alluri district is the ethnic based district of Andhra Pradesh. Some of the villages in the district are located in remote areas, with no access to the hospitals for treatment of the patients. Therefore, traditionally some plants are being used for the treatment.

The district lies between 17° – 17' and 18°-21' of Northern latitude and in between 80° – 53' and 82° – 50' in Eastern longitude. It is bounded on the North partly by the Odisha State Partly by Chattisgarh State and partly by Telangana State on the South by Anakapalli, Kakinada and East Godavari Districts on the West covered by Godavari River and East by Vijayanagaram District with 22

mandals of which 11 (Chintapalli, Koyyuru, G.K.Veedhi, G.Madugula, Paderu, Pedabayalu, Munchingiput, Hukumpeta, Dumbriguda, Araku valley and Ananthagiri) mandals are the study area in Paderu agency. It is bounded on the north partly by Orissa state and partly by Vizianagaram district, on south by Rampachodavaram, on west by Orissa state and east by Anakapalli, The entire agency track covers 6,298 Km² i. e., 56.4% of the total geographical area of the district. The total tribal population in the study area is 2,739,919 of which Valmiki are 70,513. Though there are publications (Rao et al. 2006, Chandel and Ramesh 2023, Rao et.al.2024) on ethnomedicine for various diseases were not observed necessitating the present study.

II. Materials and Methods

Interviews were conducted with Valmiki *Vaidhyas* at their dwellings during 2008-2011. During oral interviews specific questions were asked and the information supplied by the informants was noted. The data were verified in different villages among the interviewers showing the same plant sample and even with the same informants on different occasions. The knowledgeable informants were taken to the field and along with the collection of plants for the voucher specimens, the use of plants as given by the tribal informants was noted. The field trips were meant for gathering information on medicinal plants used by them, the method and time of collection, ingredients used, mode of application, dosage and duration were recorded. In 36 pockets of the study area, 75 *vaidhyas* and practitioners were consulted. Each medicinal practice was cross checked with at least 3-4 informants. Plant identifications were made with the help of Flora of the Presidency of Madras (Gamble, 1935).

III. Enumeration

The plants are arranged in an alphabetical order with botanical name followed by family, vernacular name (VN), English name (E), location (L), method, mode and duration of the treatment. Plants and practices marked with an asterisk (*) are considered to be new or less known.

***Abrus precatorius* L.** Fabaceae, VN: Guriginja, Guruvinda E: Crab's eye

Two spoonfuls of root extract mixed in a glass of milk is administered once a day for 3 days for epilepsy.

*Bark paste mixed with 50 ml of water is given for easy delivery.

*Root paste mixed with water is administered in two tea spoonfuls once a day till cure for paralysis.

***Abutilon indicum* (L.) Sweet** Malvaceae VN: Tuttura benda, E: Indian abutilon

*Root paste mixed with half tea glass of water is administered daily twice for epilepsy.

***Acalypha indica* L.** Euphorbiaceae, VN: Kuppinta E: Indian Acalypha

Leaves with leaves of *Justicia adhatoda*, *Eclipta prostrata*, *Centella asiatica*, *Phyllanthus amarus*, *Coccinea indica*, and *Momordica charantia* are taken in equal quantities and ground and made into pills of soapnut seed size. One pill is administered with rice cunjee or buttermilk twice a day for 3 days for jaundice.

***Adenanthera pavonina* L.** Mimosaceae, VN: Bandigurvinda E: Coral wood tree

Root bark with seeds of *Withania somnifera* and tuberous roots of *Asparagus racemosus* are taken in equal quantities and ground. 2 spoonfuls of paste mixed with a spoonful of honey is administered daily twice for 5 days for asthma.

***Alangium salvifolium* (L. f.) Wang.** Alangiaceae, VN: Uduga chettu E: Sage-leaved alangium

Stem bark paste mixed with root paste of *Achyranthes aspera* is administered twice a day till cure neurological weakness.

***Barleria prionitis* L.** Acanthaceae, VN: Mullugorinta E: Thorn nail dye

*Root paste mixed with half tea glass of water is administered twice a day for 5 days for asthma.

***Bauhinia vahlii* Wight & Arn.** Caesalpiniaceae, VN: Addaku, E: Camel's foot climber

*Tender leaves along with tender leaves of *Artemisia vulgaris*, *Ricinus communis* and roots of *Rubus ellipticus* are ground and administered twice a day for 2 days for amorrhoea.

***Caesalpinia bonduc* (L.) Roxb.** Caesalpiniaceae, VN: Gaccha E: Fever nut

Root with stem barks of *Trema orientalis* and *Securinega virosa* are taken in equal quantities and ground, paste made into pills of pea seed size. 2 Pills administered once a day till cure for haemorrhoids.

***Dalbergia lanceolaria* L. f.** Fabaceae, VN: Saki chettu H: Takoli

*Stem bark paste along with *Mirabilis jalapa* tuber paste is administered twice a day for 2 days for jaundice.

***Dillenia pentagyna* Roxb.** Dilleniaceae, VN: Chinna uvva chettu, E: Dog teak

Ripened fruit is eaten for abdominal pain for abdominal pain.

***Diospyros sylvatica* Roxb.** Ebenaceae, VN: Pilli chettu

Stem bark paste mixed with half tea glass of water is administered on full moon day, half-moon day and again on full-moon day for fits.

***Drynaria quercifolia* (L.) Sm.** Polypodiaceae, VN: Kalanti bheda, Raachilaka mandhu,

A spoonful of rhizome paste mixed with 2 spoonfuls of water is administered once a day for 2 days for chest pain.

*Root paste along with root paste of *Solanum indicum* is given in doses of 10 g tablets twice a day for 4 days for fits.

***Emilia sonchifolia* (L.) DC.** Asteraceae, VN: Mushakani

A spoonful of whole plant paste along with a spoonful of honey is administered daily twice for 4 days bronchial disorders.

***Eryngium foetidum* L.** Apiaceae VN: Kerala kothimeera, Pondu goch

*Leaf paste is anointed on the body for fever.

***Gloriosa superba* L.** Liliaceae, VN: Vanka vajram E: Superb lily

*Root paste mixed with half tea glass of water is administered twice a day for 2 days for cough.

***Girardinia diversifolia* (Link) Friis** Urticaceae VN: Dulagondi

Leaf paste along with powder of pepper mixed with *Pongamia pinnata* oil is applied on effected parts for scabies.

****Hemionitis arifolia* (Burm. f.) Moor** Adiantaceae VN: Kenneris, Ramabanam

Fifty g of leaf paste is administered daily twice for cough.

***Hygrophila auriculata* (Schum.) Heine** Acanthaceae, VN: Kokilaksamu E: Long-leaved barleria

*Leaf or root paste mixed with half tea glass of water is administered thrice a day for cough.

***Lagerstroemia parviflora* Roxb.** Lythraceae, VN: Sennangi

Leaves with leaves of *Mangifera indica* and *Syzygium cumini* are taken in equal quantities and ground.

2 spoonfuls of paste is administered daily twice for 3 days for stomach pain.

***Mallotus philippensis* (Lam.) Muell-Arg.** Euphorbiaceae VN: Yerra sinduram E: Spoon weed

*Root paste mixed with *Pongamia pinnata* oil is applied on the effected areas once a day till cure for scabies.

***Mirabilis jalapa* L.** Nyctaginaceae, VN: Davala Malthi, E: 4 '0 clock plant

20 g of tuberous root paste with 10 ml of urine of man is administered thrice a day with empty stomach for 4 days for jaundice.

*Root paste mixed with root pastes of *Asparagus racemosus* and *Rubia cordifolia* are administered twice a day till cure for leucorrhoea.

***Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.** Fabaceae, VN: Dula dama E: Cowitch

*Root paste mixed with half tea glass of water is administered twice a day for helminthiasis.

2 spoonfuls of seed paste with a glass of milk is administered twice a day for 5 days nervous disorders.

***Oroxylum indicum* (L.) Vent.** Bignoniaceae VN: Pumpena E: Indian trumpet-flower

*Bark paste mixed with half tea glass of hot water is given at the time of delivery for easy delivery.

*Root paste mixed with half tea glass of water is administered daily once till cure fits.

***Plumbago zeylanica* L.** Plumbaginaceae, VN: Tella chitramoolam E: Ceylon lead wort

Roots ground with leaves of *Pergularia daemia* and *Vanda tessellata*. Paste is plastered and bandaged for 21 days for bone fracture.

***Semecarpus anacardium* L. f.** Anacardiaceae, VN: Nalla jeedi E: Marking nut

Stem bark paste mixed with urine of an infant mildly heated and applied on the affected areas daily once till cure for cuts and wounds.

***Smilax zeylanica* L.** Smilacaceae, VN: Kummari baddu E: Rough bind weed

*Root paste mixed with half tea glass of water is administered once a day for giddiness.

***Tagetes erecta* L.** Asteraceae, VN: Banthi pulu E: Aztec marigold, Big marigold.

The juice of the flower is used as eye drops once a day till cure for eye diseases.

****Thunbergia alata* Boj. ex Sims** Acanthaceae, VN: Thalagudda teega E: Yellow winged rainbow creeper

250 g of flowers are heated lightly and placed on the abdomen and bandaged for a night. Note: advisable to below 3 months pregnant women abortion.

A spoonful of root paste mixed in a half glass of hot water is administered once a day for 3 days leucorrhoea and menorrhagia.

***Tinospora cordifolia* (Willd.) Miers ex Hook. f. & Thoms.,** Menispermaceae VN: Thippa theega E: Gulancha tinospora

*Stem paste mixed with half tea glass of hot water is administered once a day for 3 days galactagogue. 5 spoonfuls of dried root powder mixed with a spoonful of castor oil is applied on the affected area once a day for 21 days for leukoderma.

***Withania somnifera* (L.) Dunal** Solanaceae VN: Pennerugadda E: Aswagandha

Tuber paste mixed with half tea glass of water is administered daily twice till cure bronchial disorders.

***Zingiber officinale* Rosc.** Zingiberaceae, VN: Allam E: Ginger

Tuber paste ground with root of *Piper longum* and leaf of *Ocimum tenuiflorum* is administered with half tea glass of water twice a day for 5 days for cough.

IV. Discussions

The present investigation is the documentation of medicinal plant and their utilization and treating various diseases. During the investigation, 31 plant species from 31 families were identified as being used to treat diseases like abdominal pain, Abortion, Asthma, bronchial disorders, bone fracture, chest pain, cuts, easy delivery, epilepsy, eye diseases, fever, fits, cough, galactagogue, giddiness, helminthiasis, haemorrhoids, jaundice, leukoderma, leucorrhoea, menorrhagia, neurological weakness, nervous disorders, paralysis, scabies, stomach pain, wounds. *Girardinia diversifolia*, *Hemionitis arifolia*, *Thunbergia alata* and 22 ethnomedicinal practices were found to be new or less known (Kirtikar and Basu, 2003).

In the present study, the Valmiki community uses the fruit of *Dillenia pentagyna* for treating abdominal pain, while the Baiga tribe of the Maikal Hills in Central India utilizes the leaf juice for muscle cuts, the bark juice for body pains, and the root juice for bone diseases. In the present study the bark paste of *Semecarpus anacardium* is used for cuts and wounds, the fruit of this plant is used for skin disease and immunity by the Baiga tribe of Maikal hills of Central India; The stem paste and root decoction of *Tinospora cardifolia* is used for galactagogue and leukoderma by the Valmiki tribe of present study, decoction of this plant used for immunity booster, it is used for fever, diabetes, blood pressure and arthritis by the Baiga tribe of Maikal hills of Central India (Chandel and Ramesh, 2023).

The Valmiki tribe of present study the root of *Abrus precatorius* used for epilepsy, while the Khonds of Visakhapatnam district used root decoction of this plant for abortion. In the present study the Valmiki tribe used the stem bark of *Diospyros sylvatica* for fits, the Khonds of Visakhapatnam district used the plant for same purposes. The stem bark paste of *Semecarpus anacardium* is used for cuts and wounds by the Valmiki's of present study, fruit paste of this plant used for menstrual disorders by the Khonds of Visakhapatnam district (Rao et. al. 2006). In the present study the valmikis used the root of *Smilax zeylanica* for giddiness, the tuber of this plant used for paralysis by the khonds of Visakhapatnam

district. The stem of *Tinospora cordifolia* used for galactagogue by the Valmiki's of present study, while the Khonds of Visakhapatnam district used for bone fracture (Nageswara Rao et al.2022).

Urgent follow-up studies on traditional tribal medicinal practices are needed to develop and standardize herbal remedies, whether from single plants or combinations, ensuring their safety and long-term benefits for human well-being.

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